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**OF PEDAGOGUES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS
THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING CREATIVITY**

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Annotation In this article, the importance of developing the creativity of pedagogic personnel in preschool educational organizations today, the necessity of using technologies for developing the speech and thinking of preschool children based on a creative approach in preschool educational organizations, an opinion about the role of creativity in the activities of educators and pedagogues held.

Key words: preschool education, pedagogue, creativity, upbringing, thinking, development, speech, technology, educator.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan says about the preschool education system, "We are raising the issue of establishing the Third Renaissance in our country as a strategic task and raising it to the level of a national idea. We consider pre-school education and school education, higher education system and scientific and cultural institutions as four integral links of the future Renaissance. We consider our kindergarten teachers, school teachers, professors and scientific and creative intellectuals to be the four pillars of the new Renaissance. Pre-school education is the first pillar and support for creating the foundation of the future. The strength of this support depends on the pedagogical personnel working in this field.

Today, human intelligence, potential and creativity are highly valued in the world community. We encounter the concept of creativity almost every day. The concept of creativity (lat. "kreate" - to create, "creative" means "creation" when translated from English). So, since it means to create creativity, it is assumed that educators should be able to teach children to approach their profession creatively, to be able

to create a creative environment, to solve problems in non-standard ways in the process of educating a creative person. The modern education system makes such demands on pedagogues that it is necessary to have a unique and creative approach to each of the educational activities organized according to it. Every lesson should be interesting and effective for students. In modern times, teaching children of preschool age, developing their creativity requires great skill from the pedagogue, devotion to his profession, creative approach to education. To do this, the educator and pedagogue must work tirelessly on himself, think creatively, and organize creative activity processes.

Pedagogues in preschool educational institutions educate children in the early stages of their development. This is a very complex and responsible task. One of the most important features of the content of education is a person's vital self-awareness, his personal life and activity are characterized by recognition as a subject of the environment in which he lives. Civil, professional and moral self-awareness is important in human development. The educational process will give effective results only if the teacher teaches students to self-educate, i.e., to consciously and actively work on themselves. Making students learn self-education methods depends on the teacher's skills and the correct organization of educational activities.

Education is a concept that serves to transfer intergenerational socio-historical and life experience, means the process of forming and improving a physically healthy, intellectually mature person under the influence of family, educational institutions, social, political and other organizations, mass media and others. In the preschool education system, which is an active part of this process, the level of development of creativity and creative abilities of pedagogues is very important. A teacher-educator does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed by consistent study and work on himself over a period of time, and it gradually improves and develops.

As in the case of any specialist, the foundation is laid in the student years for future pedagogues to have creativity and it is consistently developed in the organization of professional activity. It is important that the pedagogue directs himself to creative activity and is able to organize this activity effectively. In the concept "On approval of the concept of the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", it is stated that "Creating conditions for the intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children in preschool educational organizations "requires revision of the current procedure of organizing the education process and introduction of modern methods of providing preschool education services."

Educators should work on themselves in order to develop their creativity, keep abreast of science and technology innovations, and avoid monotony in the educational process. Self-creative activation is not whether a person fully manifests and develops his capabilities in creative activity, but rather organizes activities in the spirit of creativity, creativity, and new ideas. It is necessary to strive to try in the educational process. According to the "creativity road map", the classes move in the following 4 directions, and the actions in them are listed as signs of creativity of pedagogues (Patti Drapeau):

- (1) demonstrate creative thinking skills;
- (2) encouraging to master the training with interest
(being able to use strategies;
- (3) innovative approach and creative approach to finding solutions to pedagogical issues;
- (4) expected result.

The pedagogical process aimed at ensuring all-round development of children is complex and diverse. Educational issues, organizational forms of educational work, various types of children's activities:

by teaching in training,
creative and rule games,
children's independent activities,
by introducing them to their own work and the work of adults,
self-service, outings,
carried out through hygienic measures.

Organization of these processes definitely requires creativity from the teacher. It is a real creativity to organize games that are not only interesting for children, but also shape their thinking, develop their worldview, and make them aware of the worlds and worlds of existence. During preschool education, children imitate the events and people they see. A pedagogue who works on himself and finds unique solutions can be a good example for children. A pedagogue with creative qualities is active in organizing professional activities, creative approach, creation of new, advanced ideas that serve to develop children's educational activities and personal qualities, independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences, also focuses on developing skills for continuous, consistent feedback about pedagogical progress with colleagues. In the opinion of foreign pedagogues, especially Patti Drapeau, "the creativity of one person, especially a teacher-educator, inspires others to organize their creative process."

In short, there will be no pedagogues without creativity. To develop creativity, to work on oneself, to show oneself, to be aware of the changes and news in the environment, in addition, in the organization of training, a pre-planned training His desire to create something new by abandoning the types creates the basis for his creative ability to become richer. An educator is not only a person who gets along easily with everyone, but also a person who chooses materials, creating the highest opportunities for children's development. Creating an opportunity for children's creative and creative development, children feeling free to express their feelings depends on the pedagogical skills and creativity of the educator.

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